

Malnutrition Prediction Using Decision Tree and Random Forest Algorithm

Althaf Shajahan

PG Scholar

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala

althafshajahan104@gmail.com

T J Jobin

Assistant Professor

Master of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kottayam, Kerala

tjjobin@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract— Malnutrition remains a significant public health concern globally, particularly affecting vulnerable populations such as infants and children. Malnutrition refers to the imbalance between the intake of nutrients and the body's requirements, leading to adverse health outcomes. Ensemble learning is a machine learning approach that combines the predictions of multiple base models to improve predictive performance. This study employs two popular ensemble techniques: Random Forest and Decision Trees. Random Forest constructs a multitude of decision trees and aggregates their predictions, while Decision Trees partition the feature space to predict the target variable. The dataset used in this study comprises features related to infant health, demographics, feeding patterns, and growth metrics. By leveraging Random Forest and Decision Trees, this research aims to identify key factors contributing to infant malnutrition and develop accurate predictive models.

Keywords— malnutrition, machine learning, ensemble, decision tree, random forest

I. INTRODUCTION

Malnutrition remains a pervasive and multifaceted challenge impacting populations worldwide, particularly among vulnerable groups such as infants and children. Defined as the inadequate or excessive consumption of nutrients relative to the body's needs, malnutrition manifests in various forms, including undernutrition, overnutrition, and micronutrient deficiencies, each presenting unique health risks and consequences.

Early detection and timely intervention are paramount in mitigating the adverse health outcomes associated with malnutrition, necessitating accurate and reliable prediction methods to identify individuals at risk. In recent years, the application of machine learning techniques, particularly ensemble learning methods, has emerged as a promising approach in predicting and managing malnutrition. Ensemble learning involves the integration of predictions from multiple base models to enhance predictive performance, leveraging the diversity of individual models to achieve superior results compared to standalone approaches.

This paper explores the role of ensemble learning methods, specifically Random Forest and Decision Trees, in predicting malnutrition among infants. By leveraging diverse features encompassing infant health metrics, demographics, feeding patterns, and growth indicators, this study seeks to develop robust predictive models capable of identifying infants at heightened risk of malnutrition. Through an analysis of the

dataset and the application of ensemble learning algorithms, this research aims to uncover significant predictors of infant malnutrition and elucidate the complex interplay of factors contributing to this critical public health issue.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- A. Jain et al.[1] extensively reviewed various Machine Learning Algorithms, analyzing their strengths and weaknesses. They employed a range of classifiers, including Random Forest, Support Vector Machine, K-Nearest Neighbours, and Logistic Regression, to predict malnutrition status in children under 5 years old. Their objective was to identify the most effective algorithm based on accuracy scores, ultimately striving for optimal predictive performance.
- B. Kar et al.[2] investigated the nutritional status of children aged 0–59 months, focusing on stunting, wasting, and concurrent stunted wasting. They explored the efficacy of various machine learning models, including regular models, Tabular Deep Learning frameworks, H2O base models, and AutoML models. Their findings highlighted the superior speed, efficiency, and accuracy of automated machine learning algorithms and Tabular Deep Learning frameworks compared to other models.
- C. Momand et al.[3] introduced a data mining approach to predict the malnutrition status of children under five years old in Afghanistan. They utilized Random Forest, PART rule induction, and Naïve Bayes classifiers on Afghanistan Nutrition SMART Survey data, comparing their results with Logistic Regression.
- D. Iqbal et al.[4] sought to classify malnutrition using a deep learning approach, focusing on significant features related to malnutrition in children aged 0-59 months. They employed Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models on Bangladesh Demographic and Health Survey 2014 (BDHS) data to predict malnutrition status.
- E. Di Martino et al.[5] explored multiple Machine Learning models using the Mini Nutritional Assessment rating scale as ground truth, addressing dataset imbalance through SMOTE and cost-sensitive learning techniques. Their findings revealed that the top-performing ML models achieved median accuracy and recall values of 94% and 92%, respectively, for predicting malnutrition risk.

III. METHODOLOGY

The primary objective of this system is to predict malnutrition in infants using machine learning algorithms to assist in early identification and intervention. This

methodology encompasses utilizing ensemble learning techniques such as Random Forest and Decision Trees on demographic, health, and anthropometric data to build predictive models. Features will be analyzed for importance to identify key factors related to malnutrition. The Proposed system has used the following algorithms:

- Random Forest Classifier
- Decision Tree Classifier

Random Forest is an ensemble learning algorithm that constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the mode of the classes (classification) or the mean prediction (regression) of the individual trees. It randomly selects a subset of features at each split, which helps to decorrelate the trees and reduce overfitting. This algorithm is known for its robustness against overfitting and its ability to handle high-dimensional datasets with noisy features.

Decision Trees, on the other hand, are a type of supervised learning algorithm used for classification and regression tasks. They partition the feature space into regions based on feature values, aiming to create branches that lead to the most pure subsets of the target variable. Decision Trees are interpretable and easy to understand, as they mimic human decision-making processes. However, they are prone to overfitting, especially with complex datasets.

Ensemble learning is a powerful machine learning technique that leverages the collective wisdom of multiple models to make more accurate predictions than any individual model could achieve alone. By combining the predictions of diverse base models, such as decision trees or neural networks, ensemble methods mitigate the weaknesses of individual models and exploit their strengths, resulting in improved overall performance.

The Methodology includes:

A. **Data Collection:**

Data collection for this project involved gathering demographic information, health records, and anthropometric measurements from infants. This included variables such as age, gender, weight, height, and bone mineral density statistics. The dataset 'dataset1.csv' loaded using pandas.

B. **Data Preprocessing**

Load the dataset, drop any irrelevant rows and reset the index. Split the dataset into features (X) and the target variable indicating malnutrition (y).

C. **Model Training**

Implement ensemble learning techniques such as Random Forest and Decision Tree classifiers using scikit-learn. Train both models using the training data.

D. **Model Evaluation**

Evaluate the performance of both Random Forest and Decision Tree models using various metrics including accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score

The following metrics are used in this for calculation

- Z-score: It is a statistical measure that indicates how many standard deviations an individual's measurement is from the mean of the reference population.

$$Z = \frac{X - \mu}{\sigma}$$

Where X is the individual's measurement (e.g. weight or height), μ is the mean of the reference population, σ is the standard deviation of the reference population.

- BMI: It is a measure of body fat based on an individual's weight and height. It is widely used as a screening tool to identify whether a person is underweight, normal weight, overweight, or obese.

$$BMI = \text{height} / \text{weight}^2$$

- Weight gain rate: It measures the rate at which a person's weight changes over a specific time period. It is often used to monitor growth in infants and children or to assess the effectiveness of nutrition interventions.

$$\text{Weight gain rate} = \frac{\text{final weight} - \text{initial weight}}{\text{time period}}$$

IV. BUILD MODEL

The steps involved in predicting malnutrition involves:

1. Import the necessary packages

```
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.ensemble import RandomForestClassifier
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, precision_score, recall_score, f1_score, confusion_matrix
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
```

2. Upload the dataset

```
data = pd.read_csv('dataset1.csv')
```

3. Split dataset into features and target variable

```
X = data.drop(columns=['OUTMAL'])
y = data['OUTMAL']
```

4. Split the dataset into training data and testing data

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, y, test_size=0.2, random_state=42)
```

5. Finding the accuracy of both the models

```
rf_accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, rf_pred)
rf_precision = precision_score(y_test, rf_pred)
rf_recall = recall_score(y_test, rf_pred)
rf_f1 = f1_score(y_test, rf_pred)
print("Random Forest Metrics:")
print("Accuracy:", rf_accuracy)
print("Precision:", rf_precision)
print("Recall:", rf_recall)
print("F1-score:", rf_f1)
```

7. Fit the model having more accuracy

```
from ensemble import y_train, X_train

rf_model = RandomForestClassifier(random_state=42)
rf_model.fit(X_train, y_train)
```

8. Functions for the calculation of Body Mass Index, Z-score and Weight gain rate.

```
def calculate_bmi(weight_kg, height_cm):
    height_m = height_cm / 100
    bmi = weight_kg / (height_m ** 2)
    return bmi

def calculate_z_score(measurement, mean, std_dev):
    z_score = (measurement - mean) / std_dev
    return z_score

def calculate_weight_gain_rate(weight_initial, weight_final, time_
    weight_gain_rate = (weight_final - weight_initial) / time_peri
    return weight_gain_rate
```

9. Prediction is made.

```
prediction = rf_model.predict([features])[0]
```

V. RESULT

The results of our study demonstrate the effectiveness of ensemble learning techniques, specifically Random Forest and Decision Tree algorithms, in predicting infant malnutrition based on a variety of health and demographic factors. The algorithm that has more accuracy used for calculating the body mass index (BMI), z-score, and weight gain rate as they play a significant roles in determining the nutritional status of infants, with higher BMI values associated with a decreased risk of malnutrition.

```
Random Forest Metrics:
Accuracy: 0.9756468797564688
Precision: 0.9453125
Recall: 0.9307692307692308
F1-score: 0.937984496124031
Decision Tree Metrics:
Accuracy: 0.9722222222222222
Precision: 0.9408284023668639
Recall: 0.9173076923076923
F1-score: 0.928919182083739
```

Malnutrition Prediction

BMD STATS:

Gender:

Age in years:

Body Weight:

Height:

Leg length:

Arm length:

Arm Circumference:

Waist Circumference:

Hip Circumference:

Result

Child's Nutritional Status:
Not Malnourished

BMI:
25.910684346898332

Z-score:
3.6

Weight Gain Rate:
58.0

VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our research endeavours to address the pressing issue of malnutrition in infants, a multifaceted challenge with significant implications for public health and child development. Through the application of ensemble learning techniques, specifically Random Forest and Decision Tree algorithms, we aimed to develop predictive models capable of identifying infants at risk of malnutrition based on a range of health and demographic features.

VII. REFERENCES

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